

Assessment Techniques

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Annotation

Assessment for learning is also referred to as formative assessment, i.e. the process of collecting and interpreting evidence for use by teachers and learners to decide where they are in their learning, where they need to go, and how best to get there. Assessment inspires us to ask these difficult questions: "Are we teaching what we think we are teaching?" "Are students learning what they are supposed to be learning?" "Is there a way to teach the subject better, thereby promoting better learning?"

Annotatsiya

Ta'lim uchun baholash, shuningdek, formativ baholash deb ataladi, ya'ni o'qituvchilar va o'quvchilar o'z ta'limda qayerda ekanliklarini, qayerga borishlari kerakligini va u erga eng yaxshi tarzda qanday erishishni hal qilish uchun foydalanish uchun dalillarni to'plash va talqin qilish jarayoni. Baholash bizni ushbu qiyin savollarni berishga ilhomlantiradi: "Biz o'zimiz o'rgatgan narsamizni o'rgatyapmizmi?" "Talabalar o'zlari o'rganishlari kerak bo'lgan narsalarni o'rganishyaptimi?" "Mavzuni yaxshiroq o'rgatish va shu orqali yaxshiroq o'rganishga yordam berishning bir usuli bormi?"

Key words: contain, objective, an integral part, major skills, evaluation

Kalit so'zlar: o'z ichiga, maqsad, ajralmas qism, asosiy ko'nikmalar, baholash

Introduction

Among the most comprehensive listing of principles of assessment for learning are those written by the QCA (Qualifications and Curriculum Authority). The authority, which is sponsored by England's Department for Children, Schools and Families, is responsible for national curriculum, assessment, and examinations. Their principal focus is on crucial aspects of assessment for learning, including how such assessment should be seen as central to classroom practice, and that all teachers should regard assessment for learning as a key professional skill.

Assessment for learning, on the other hand, occurs at all stages of the learning process. Students are encouraged to take an active role, become self-regulated learners and leave school able and confident to continue learning throughout their lives. Assessment for learning is also referred to as formative assessment, i.e. the process of collecting and interpreting evidence for use by teachers and learners to decide where they are in their learning, where they need to go, and how best to get there (Assessment Reform Group, 2002). It is a process by which assessment information is used by teachers to adjust their teaching strategies and by students to adjust their learning strategies. AfL encourages learning and promotes motivation by emphasising progress and achievement rather than failure.

Techniques used in daily assessments:

Assessment is an essential tool to measure the level of learning outcome of the taught. I use it as a sharp weapon to shoot the target.

Assessment begins from framing essential questions considering in mind the difficulty level of the taught. It is content oriented amalgamated with extrapolatory questions to promote lateral thinking.

To make evaluation a true index of learners' attainment I have to concentrate to test on each language ability. Questions are of different difficulty levels—easy, average and difficult. Written tests contain a judicious mixture of different types of questions, i.e., objective, true-false, matching, short answers type, very short answer type and essay type. Oral testing is an integral part of it.

I have developed suitable tools for the assessment of students for gradation of leaning outcome through CCE. Though line by line correction by the teacher is not made rather their mistakes are pointed out and symbols for their self correction is marked. For example, sp=spelling, tn=Tense, pun=Punctuation etc. This is one of the very effective ways of correction for higher classes in language teaching. Language teaching includes four major skills to be mastered. They are:

- a. Listening
- b. Speaking
- c. Reading and
- d. Writing

Besides them, provocation of critical thinking needs to be encouraged too.

Techniques for the provocation of the same are to:

- a. Provide them opportunity to listen to the English language as much as possible
- b. Ask to speak the language by putting the questions from the content heard
- c. Ask them read the content loudly (in early stages) for pronunciation, rhythm, and intonation correction
- d. Provide home work/ class work to strengthen writing skill. This is the integration of all skills to concretize the learning outcome.
- e. Dictation for listening and writing
- f. Crossword puzzle to read and write.
- g. True-false for reading, listening and speaking
- h. Formation of sentences with given words to think and write.
- i. Finding synonym and antonym to assess understanding and IQ
- j. Exposure to grammar challenges to concretise correct writing
- k. Writing story/ passage/ report/ notice/ factual description/ letter to enable them communicate with the world (Class X).
- l. Writing answers of textual questions to assess expression and understanding
- m. Recording of marks obtained for further analysis and feed back

Using results as a resource for improvement

Evaluation of the oral and written tests is recorded, analysis is done, timely feedback is provided, model answers are prepared and displayed on LCD. The students are asked to differentiate their original answers

with the model one, discussion of the pros and cons on the same is made in the class. It finally results in outstanding performance.

Conclusion

Classroom Assessment Techniques (CATs) are generally simple, non-graded, anonymous, in-class activities designed to give you and your students useful feedback on the teaching-learning process as it is happening.

The Background Knowledge Probe is a short, simple questionnaire given to students at the start of a course, or before the introduction of a new unit, lesson or topic. It is designed to uncover students' pre-conceptions.

The Minute Paper tests how students are gaining knowledge, or not. The instructor ends class by asking students to write a brief response to the following questions: “What was the most important thing you learned during this class?” and “What important question remains unanswered?”

The Muddiest Point is one of the simplest CATs to help assess where students are having difficulties. The technique consists of asking students to jot down a quick response to one question: “What was the muddiest point in [the lecture, discussion, homework assignment, film, etc.]?” The term “muddiest” means “most unclear” or “most confusing.”

The What's the Principle? CAT is useful in courses requiring problem-solving. After students figure out what type of problem they are dealing with, they often must decide what principle(s) to apply in order to solve the problem. This CAT provides students with a few problems and asks them to state the principle that best applies to each problem.

Defining Features Matrix: Prepare a handout with a matrix of three columns and several rows. At the top of the first two columns, list two distinct concepts that have potentially confusing similarities (e.g. hurricanes vs. tornados, Picasso vs. Matisse). In the third column, list the important characteristics of both concepts in no particular order. Give your students the handout and have them use the matrix to identify which characteristics belong to each of the two concepts. Collect their responses, and you'll quickly find out which characteristics are giving your students the most trouble.

Why Should I Use CATs?

CATs can be used to improve the teaching and learning that occurs in a class. More frequent use of CATs can...

- Provide just-in-time feedback about the teaching-learning process

- Provide information about student learning with less work than traditional assignments (tests, papers, etc.)

- Encourage the view that teaching is an ongoing process of inquiry, experimentation, and reflection

- Help students become better monitors of their own learning

- Help students feel less anonymous, even in large courses

- Provide concrete evidence that the instructor cares about learning

How Should I Use CATs?

Results from CATs can guide teachers in fine-tuning their teaching strategies to better meet student needs. A good strategy for using CATs is the following.

Decide what you want to assess about your students’ learning from a CAT.

Choose a CAT that provides this feedback, is consistent with your teaching style, and can be implemented easily in your class.

Explain the purpose of the activity to students, and then conduct it.

After class, review the results, determine what they tell you about your students’ learning, and decide what changes to make, if any.

References

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